

STUDIES IN THE SUBSTITUTED SUCCINIC ACIDS. PART I.

BY RAFAT HUSAIN SIDDIQUI AND SALAH-UD-DIN.

o-Chloro, *o*- and *p*-methoxyphenyl and phenylsuccinic acids and their derivatives have been obtained.

Phenyl and substituted phenylsuccinic acids were required for an investigation but as one of us (S) left the University the work had to be stopped and consequently we publish the results so far achieved. As a result of this investigation *o*-chloro-, *o*- and *p*-methoxyphenyl and phenylsuccinic acids and their derivatives have been obtained by the method of Lapworth and Wikas (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 796). It consists in condensing the aldehyde and ethyl cyanoacetate in the presence of piperidine when arylidene cyanoacetate results. This on addition of hydrogen cyanide yields a product which on hydrolysis with boiling hydrochloric acid gives the desired succinic acid. It has been incidentally noticed that the arylidene cyanoacetate on addition of hydrogen cyanide in every case gives a crystalline product but its nitrogen value is much too high for α,β -dicyano- β -aryl propionate and it is hoped that this work will be taken up again.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Commercial *o*-toluidine was freed from the *para* isomer by converting it into insoluble *o*-toluidine hydroferrocyanide by bringing together aqueous solutions of the hydrochloride of the base and sodium ferrocyanide. On decomposing the salt with sodium hydroxide the base distilled at 198°, acetyl derivative, m.p. 110°. The pure base (as hydrochloride) was diazotised at -5° and on adding freshly reduced copper powder the mixture was warmed at 60° to decompose the diazonium compound when the *o*-chlorotoluene separated and distilled at 156°. For the preparation of *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde from *o*-chlorotoluene, oxidation with chromium oxychloride in carbon bisulphide (b.p. 205-10°, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1888, 53, 803), or chloroform solution (*ibid.*, 1907, 91, 261), was used and the aldehyde was obtained as a semi-solid mass, b.p. 210-14°, but when the aldehyde was prepared by converting *o*-chlorotoluene into *o*-chlorobenzal chloride and hydrolysing the latter with either oxalic or sulphuric acid, it distilled at 210-14° but soon turned into a solid, m.p. 28°, semicarbazone, m.p. 225°. The aldehyde on keeping for a fortnight melted at 54° and after three months had m.p. 125° and it continued to emit aldehydic smell. In the present investigation freshly distilled aldehyde was used.

*Ethyl α -cyano- β -(*o*-chlorophenyl)-acrylate.*—A mixture of freshly distilled *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde (40 g.), ethyl cyanoacetate (35 g.) and piperidine (2 c.c.) was allowed to stand for 12 hours. The ester separated in needles, m.p. 225°. It was filtered at the pump and washed with a little alcohol. It is soluble in acetone, chloroform and difficultly so in alcohol, yield 51 g.

Addition of Hydrogen Cyanide to the above Ester.—A solution of the ester (48 g.) and potassium cyanide (14 g. in 14 c.c. of water) in alcohol (300 c.c.) was allowed to stand for 72 hours. On removal of the solvent a viscous oil separated and no attempt was made to obtain it in the crystalline form.

**o*-Chlorophenylsuccinic Acid.*—The above oily compound (55 g.) was hydrolysed by boiling with concentrated hydrochloric acid (50 c.c.) and water (50 c.c.). On cooling, *o*-chlorophenylsuccinic acid separated in needles, m.p. 155°; recrystallised from ether-petroleum ether mixture, m.p. 177°. It is soluble in ether, acetone, ethyl acetate, alcohol and hot water and insoluble in chloroform, benzene and petroleum ether. (Found in substance dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 52.57; H, 4.08; Cl, 15.08. $C_{10}H_7O_4Cl$ requires C, 52.5; H, 3.9; Cl, 15.6 per cent).

**o*-Chlorophenylsuccinic Anhydride.*—A mixture of *o*-chlorophenylsuccinic acid and acetic anhydride was kept simmering for 5 hours and on removal of acetic anhydride in *vacuo* the residue crystallised from chloroform-petroleum ether mixture, m.p. 119-20°.

*Monoanilide of *o*-Chlorophenylsuccinic Acid.*—*o*-Chlorophenylsuccinic anhydride (0.1 g.) and an equal proportion of aniline were brought together in benzene and from the solution on warming for a minute or two the anilide separated as snow-white needles, m.p. 168°. (Found in substance dried at 100° in *vacuo*: N, 5.84. $C_{16}H_{13}O_2N$ requires N, 5.2 per cent).

*Ethyl α -cyano- β -(*p*-methoxyphenyl) acrylate* was obtained from anisaldehyde (110 g.), ethyl cyanoacetate (90 g.) and piperidine (2 c.c.) as needles, m.p. 84°, yield 158 g. It is soluble in chloroform, ethyl acetate, benzene, ether, acetone and hot water, insoluble in petroleum ether and difficultly soluble in alcohol. (Found in substance dried in *vacuo*: C, 67.22; H, 5.82; N, 6.36. $C_{13}H_{13}O_3N$ requires C, 67.5; H, 5.6; N, 6.1 per cent).

Addition of Hydrogen Cyanide to the Above.—A mixture of the above acrylate (150 g.), potassium cyanide (30 g. in 40 c.c. of water) and alcohol (1500 c.c.) was kept at room temperature for 48 hours. Three quarters of the solvent were distilled and the residue on cooling at 0° separated in light violet wooly needles. It was recrystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 73°. The nitrogen value does not agree with $\alpha\beta$ -dicyano- β -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-

propionate. (Found in substance dried over P_2O_5 in *vacuo* : N, 15.98. $C_{13}H_{13}O_3N_2$ requires N, 11.3 per cent).

p-Methoxyphenylsuccinic Acid.—The above ester (130 g.) was hydrolysed with concentrated hydrochloric acid (200 c.c.) and water (150 c.c.) under reflux for 4 hours. The oil which separated on cooling deposited needles (105 g.). From acetone white needles, m.p. 206°, were obtained. (Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo* : C, 59.00; H, 5.56. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{12}O_5$: C, 58.9; H, 5.4 per cent).

The anhydride was prepared by the usual method and crystallised from chloroform-petroleum ether in needles, m.p. 92-93°. Monoanilide, m.p. 122°; *p*-methoxyphenylsuccinil was obtained when the monoanilide was heated above its m.p. in a sulphuric acid bath and crystallised from benzene, m.p. 140-42°. Mono-*o*-toluidide, m.p. 156° (white needles); *o*-tolil, m.p. 170°; mono-*p*-toluidide, m.p. 176°; *p*-tolil, m.p. 140-42°.

Ethyl α -cyano- β -(*o*-methoxyphenyl)-acrylate was obtained as light yellow needles, m.p. 77°; hydrogen cyanide addition product of the acrylate was obtained as colourless needles from alcohol, m.p. 85°. (Found in substance dried over P_2O_5 in *vacuo* : N, 16.52. $C_{13}H_{13}O_3N_2$ requires N, 11.3 per cent).

o-Methoxyphenylsuccinic Acid.—The above hydrogen cyanide addition product of the acrylate on hydrolysis with concentrated hydrochloric acid gave *o*-methoxyphenylsuccinic acid (white needles), m.p. 182°.

Ethyl α -cyano- β -phenylacrylate separated as needles from petrol, m.p. 54°. The hydrogen cyanide addition product of the acrylate was obtained as needles, m.p. 69° (Ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dicyano- β -phenylpropionate, prepared by a different method, melts at 64°, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 1471). The nitrogen value of this is also too high. (Found in substance dried over P_2O_5 : N, 19.04. $C_{12}H_{13}O_2N_2$ requires N, 13.0 per cent). The mother-liquor from the hydrogen cyanide addition product in every case gave the same acid as the crystalline derivative. The hydrogen cyanide addition product on hydrolysis by the usual method gave phenylsuccinic acid, which was obtained as colourless needles from ether, m.p. 172°.

The authors wish to express their thanks to the Honorary Secretary, Indian Chemical Society, for some of the nitrogen analyses. Other micro analyses were done by Dr. Ing. A. Schoeller, Berlin.

THE CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
MUSLIM UNIVERSITY,
ALIGARH.

Received November 4, 1941.